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Does income inequality influence health vulnerability to pollution? Evidence from France*

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Abstract

This study investigates whether income inequality within a population influences the health effects of pollution. Specifically, we empirically estimate the causal impact of particulate matter (PM₁₀) on mortality in France, using wind direction as an instrumental variable, and explore how income inequality modifies this relationship. Our findings reveal a statistically and economically significant impact of pollution exposure on the mortality of individuals aged 50 or older, which intensifies in municipalities with higher levels of income inequality. More precisely, while the effect of PM₁₀ is not significant in municipalities with the lowest levels of disparities, it is significant for the others and increases with the level of inequality within the municipalities. The impact of PM₁₀ on the mortality of individuals aged 50 or older in the top 33% of municipalities with the highest inequality is up to twice as large as in municipalities with intermediate levels of inequality. This result is particularly striking given that it concerns a country like France, which has relatively low income inequality. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the potential underlying mechanisms, we develop a theoretical model and empirically test its predictions. We conclude that the observed variation in vulnerability to pollution across municipalities, stratified by inequality levels, could have been but is not attributable to differences in public health expenditure, pollution exposure (between and within municipalities), or poverty prevalence and intensity. Our results suggest that inequality plays a significant role in environmental health, worthy of further research.

Keywords: Income inequality, Air pollution, Particulate matter, Mortality, Health expenditures.

JEL classification: I14, Q53, Q56.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The harmful effects of air pollution on health and adult mortality have been extensively documented in the empirical literature. The Lancet Commission on Pollution and Health recently reported that air pollution accounts for approximately 6.7 million premature deaths annually, accounting for one in eight deaths worldwide (Fuller et al., 2022). In France, Pascal et al. (2016) find that $PM_{2.5}$ contributes to 9% of total adult mortality. Moreover, this body of literature emphasizes that the detrimental health effects of pollution are unequally distributed across the population (see, e.g., Laurent et al., 2007; Cakmak et al., 2011; Graff Zivin and Neidell, 2013; Lavaine, 2015; Giaccherini et al., 2021; von Hinke and Sorensen, 2023 or Sun et al., 2024). In particular, many studies have examined the role of income in pollution-related mortality and emphasize the greater vulnerability of disadvantaged agents (see, e.g., Arceo et al., 2016, or Bowe et al., 2019). Two main reasons are typically identified to explain why. First, wealthier individuals are more likely to live and work in better socioeconomic conditions, making them less exposed to pollution. Second, they have better access to healthcare and are more likely to adopt healthier behaviors (including avoidance behaviors), thus, reducing their vulnerability. However, what about the potential role of income distribution in shaping vulnerability to pollution? This paper explores whether and how inequality within a municipality may influence the health impacts of pollution, through both theoretical and empirical analyses.

Another body of literature examines the relationship between health and inequality (excluding pollution concerns) and identifies two main hypotheses: the Absolute Income Hypothesis and the Income Inequality Hypothesis (see among others Wagstaff and van Doorslaer, 2000, Truesdale and Jencks, 2016, or Chen and Gotway Crawford, 2012). According to the former, health is primarily influenced by absolute income rather than relative income or inequality. While income has a positive but concave effect on health—meaning that its marginal impact decreases as income rises—inequality itself has no intrinsic effect on health. Therefore, any observed association between inequality and health outcomes arises solely due to this concavity effect. On the contrary, the latter hypothesis argues that health is impacted by income inequality within society, meaning that income inequalities per se affect the population’s health (Wilkinson, 1997). In this view, an increase in income does not necessarily lead to an improvement in overall health. The mechanisms behind this relationship include psychological and social pressures, differential enforcement of laws, imbalanced distribution of political influence, unequal access to resources, or deteriorating public services.

This paper lies at the intersection of these two important areas of research, aiming to explore how income inequality may shape the impact of pollution on health outcomes. We contend that it is crucial to examine this specific source of mortality, as income inequality may not only exacerbate vulnerability to pollution but also lead to unequal exposure. Despite the growing body of literature

on environmental health, this interaction has been explored only to a limited extent. Among the few exceptions, Hill et al. (2019) focus on the United States and show that particulate matter $PM_{2.5}$ has a more pronounced negative effect on average life expectancy in states with a higher concentration of income in the top 10% of the income distribution. The present paper distinguishes itself by being the first to analyze the effect of income inequality on health vulnerability to pollution at a low level of aggregation (i.e., municipality-level). More precisely, we conduct an empirical analysis of more than 35,000 French municipalities for the years 2000 to 2015. As a baseline, we estimate a fixed effects model, that controls for time-invariant differences across locations and overall trends, to test the relationship between pollution exposure and the age-standardized mortality rate in a given municipality. To perform this estimation, we use annual total mortality outcomes from the French Epidemiology Center on Medical Causes of Death (CepiDC), and the mean pollution concentrations drawn from a unique and detailed dataset compiled by the French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks (Ineris). An instrumental variables strategy based on meteorological factors is used to avoid simultaneity problems. Then, we explore whether inequality indicators influence the impact of PM_{10} on mortality. To this end, we employ a range of inequality indicators: the interdecile gap, interquartile range, Gini coefficient, and the income share of the top 10%. This comprehensive dataset enables us to examine whether the potential effect of inequality on mortality stems from individual factors within municipalities, rather than from broader local factors.

We find a statistically and economically significant relationship between pollution exposure and mortality rates among the elderly, which increases in municipalities with a higher level of income inequality. More precisely, we obtain that while the effect of PM_{10} is not significant in municipalities with the lowest inequality, it is significant for others and increases with the level of inequality within municipalities. The effect of PM_{10} on the mortality of individuals aged 50 or more in the 33% municipalities with the highest levels of inequality is up to twice the effect for intermediary inequality municipalities. A back-of-the-envelope calculation, based on the value of statistical life estimated for this specific age category in France, indicates that the corresponding cost of exposure to PM_{10} in France is 4.4 billion euros per year, with up to two-thirds of this cost incurred by municipalities among the top 33% most unequal.

Then, we seek to understand the potential mechanisms behind this empirical result with the help of a theoretical model. As regards the theoretical literature, there is a growing number of papers dealing with longevity as an endogenous variable, dependent on health expenditure and/or environmental quality. A part of this literature examines the interactions between health and economic growth with demographic features, while another considers the mutual effects of health expenditure and environmental quality on longevity to analyze the interplay between growth and the environment (see, e.g., Raffin and Seegmuller, 2017). However, the question of inequality is rarely considered in

models with adult mortality. Among exceptions, Castelló-Climent and Doménech (2008) assumes that the socioeconomic status of the family conditions an individual’s life expectancy, and hence explains why income inequality may be harmful to human capital accumulation. However, these authors do not consider the environment. Closer to our work, Constant (2019) goes further by considering a life expectancy among heterogeneous agents endogenously determined by their human capital and pollution. However, these papers do not take into account how individuals may actively shape their own life expectancy. In our study, we incorporate health investments and adopt a distinct approach, as our aim is not to explore the dynamic formation of inequality and its consequences in terms of pollution-related adult mortality and growth. Instead, we focus on a more straightforward examination of how a given level of income inequality in a specific municipality might influence the average mortality rate in that area.¹

We use a partial equilibrium model that involves two different agents living in the same area. The health of each agent depends on both public and private health expenditures in line with Bhattacharya and Qiao (2007) and Raffin and Seegmuller (2017). While public health services are available to everyone, private health spending introduces inequality in vulnerability to pollution, which can lead to disparities in health outcomes. With this model, we emphasize several mechanisms through which inequality may affect the vulnerability of the population to pollution. Typically, it may occur through the effect on individual income as well as the global stock of wealth in the economy, and the difference in public health expenditure, or pollution exposure.

Back to the data, we test the potential mechanisms identified in the model. We start by clarifying the potential confounders that could explain this result but are already addressed through our empirical methodology (e.g., age distribution, median income, time-invariant municipal characteristics, factors varying over time but common to the entire territory). We identify that the influence of inequality is not attributable to differences in public health expenditure (healthcare infrastructure and ratio of doctors per inhabitant) between municipalities, or to differences in terms of pollution exposure between and within municipalities. We show that these effects are not attributable to differences in financial resources available for private health expenditure (i.e., poverty rates and levels) within municipalities either. Thus, the comparison between our theoretical model and empirical results suggests that the effect of inequality on vulnerability to pollution may be related to the choice of private health spending, its determinants, and/or effectiveness.

Finally, note that while the literature on the effect of income inequality on health (without pollution) often finds a significant impact among large (often US) counties but not smaller geographic scale (see, e.g. Chen and Gotway Crawford, 2012), we find a significant effect of inequality at the municipal level and in France, known for relatively small inequality levels. We conclude that inequal-

1. Thus, we depart from these existing models, disregarding dynamic elements and growth considerations.

ity matters for environmental health and warrants further empirical studies to test the mechanisms operating at an even smaller disaggregation level.

The paper is organized as follows. We detail the data and empirical strategy in Section 2. We present our empirical results in Section 3. We establish a theoretical model in Section 4 to identify potential mechanisms that are empirically tested in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes, and technical details are relegated to the Appendix.

2. DATA AND EMPIRICAL STRATEGY

2.1. Data and summary statistics

Table 1 presents the summary statistics of the panel dataset used for this paper, which includes more than 35,000 municipalities over 16 years from 2000 to 2015. We construct a unique database merging dataset on mortality rates by age range, pollution measures, disposable income per consumption unit, inequality indicators, and weather measures at the municipality and year level.

The mean of pollution concentrations in $ug/m3$ are drawn from a unique and detailed dataset compiled by the French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks (Ineris) for France. We choose to focus on Particulate Matter less than ten microns in diameter (PM_{10}).² This specific pollutant is commonly used in the epidemiological literature when focusing on health, as it represents a significant risk for health. Measures of PM_{10} are made available at the municipal level for the years 2000 to 2015 by Ineris. More precisely, this dataset results from the combination of modeled data³, and observational data⁴, spread over the territory to have the most accurate representation of the evolution of air pollution levels in France at the municipality level. We define a dummy that indicates whether the average concentration of pollution for PM_{10} was above $40 \mu g/m3$.⁵

For each municipality, annual total mortality outcomes were obtained from the French Epidemiology Centre on Medical Causes of Death (CepiDC) from 2000 to 2015. We dispose of the exact number of deaths by age category (less than 15 years old; 15 to 49 years old; 50 years old or more) at the municipality level.^{6,7} We construct a measure for mortality rate using population and birth from the French National Institute for Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE). Population by age

2. Our analysis being conducted starting from 2001, we cannot use finer pollution data such as $PM_{2.5}$, as measurements for these are only available from 2009.

3. The CHIMERE multi-scale model is designed to produce daily forecasts of pollutants and make long-term simulations.

4. The French monitoring stations network is composed of Certified Associations of Air Quality Monitoring (ASQAA).

5. <https://www.airparif.asso.fr/reglementation/recommandations-oms>.

6. To preserve anonymization for health data corresponding to at least 5 deaths per municipality, CEPIDc has computed age categories instead of exact age.

7. In the administrative divisions of France, the municipality is one of the three levels of government below the departmental and national levels.

Table 1 – Summary Statistics

Variables	<15	15-49	=>50	Total
A. Mortality variables				
Mortality rate (%000)	0.300 (0.594)	1.183 (0.910)	26.52 (10.76)	9.559 (13.76)
Age standardized mortality rate (per 100 000)	10.33 (5.016)	10.56 (5.316)	10.55 (5.185)	10.48 (5.179)
Number of death	0.757 (2.248)	5.313 (13.46)	79.21 (212.5)	29.12 (129.6)
Age specific population	2236.6 (5096.4)	4605.5 (11806.3)	3086.9 (8248.1)	3339.0 (8953.7)
B. Independent variables				
Mean PM ₁₀ pollution concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	23.62 (4.126)	23.53 (4.113)	23.57 (4.080)	23.57 (4.106)
C. Weather variables				
Temperature	11.90 (1.691)	11.89 (1.706)	11.89 (1.690)	11.89 (1.696)
Precipitation	2.183 (0.657)	2.190 (0.662)	2.182 (0.658)	2.185 (0.659)
Maximum wind speed	6.697 (1.169)	6.694 (1.180)	6.686 (1.168)	6.692 (1.172)
Wind mean direction	202.0 (22.72)	202.3 (23.17)	202.2 (23.19)	202.2 (23.03)
North wind mean direction	.0003 (.017)	.0003 (.017)	.0003 (.017)	.0003 (.017)
East wind mean direction	.002 (.053)	.002 (.053)	.002 (.053)	.002 (.053)
South wind mean direction	.842 (.364)	.842 (.364)	.842 (.364)	.842 (.364)
West wind mean direction	.154 (.361)	.154 (.361)	.154 (.361)	.154 (.361)
D. Income and inequality indicators				
Median of income per unit of consumption	18215.3 (4003.0)	18326.3 (4063.2)	18319.6 (4090.8)	18289.0 (4054.0)
Interdecile ratio - d9/d1	8.650 (371.2)	9.539 (391.5)	9.539 (391.5)	9.254 (385.1)
Interquartile range - Q3-Q1	11744.8 (3043.9)	11787.6 (3136.8)	11798.1 (3134.3)	11777.7 (3107.0)
Income share of the top 10 %	0.193 (0.0150)	0.192 (0.0150)	0.192 (0.0150)	0.193 (0.0150)
Gini coefficient	0.302 (0.0492)	0.301 (0.0491)	0.301 (0.0491)	0.301 (0.0492)
Observations	52560	55716	55716	55716

Note: The period covered in the analysis is 2000 to 2015, and the unit of analysis is the municipality-age-year. There are 55716 observations in the studied sample.

is only available at the census year while births are available yearly for each municipality. To define an age-specific mortality rate between each census year at the municipality level, we estimate the yearly population by age removing deaths from the previous year. We assume that population will grow by the number of births and that this will increase the age 1 category.⁸ Hence, we divide the number of deaths in a year by the estimated population for this year. As two municipalities with the same age-specific mortality rates correspond to different overall death if their age distribution is different, we compute an overall age-standardized mortality rate for overall death. The World Health Organization indicates that "the age-standardized mortality rate is a weighted average of the age-specific mortality rates per 100 000 persons, where the weights are the proportions of persons in the corresponding age groups of the WHO standard population." Here, we add a weight corresponding to the proportions of persons in the corresponding age groups of the standard population in 2006 to account for the population structure.

Then, we use several control variables recognized as determinants of pollution concentration in the literature. We dispose of daily weather data from the French meteorological data monitoring - METEO France. More particularly, we use mean temperature under shelter (24 observations), precipitation height, maximal mean of wind speed, and wind direction from 187 weather monitoring stations.⁹ Some municipalities do not have weather monitoring stations whereas others have more than one. Hence, we attribute, to each municipality, the yearly average weather data of the closest monitoring station. To do so, we use the geographical coordinates of the weather monitoring station as well as the geographical coordinates of the center of the municipality. Then, we compute distances and look for the shortest distance. The maximum distance to a given municipality is 87 kilometers.

We also dispose of several income variables and inequality indicators per consumption unit at the year and municipality level from INSEE: the median income, interdecile gap (d9/d1), interquartile range (Q3-Q1), and the income share of the top 10 %. We split these variables into tercile to compare more unequal municipalities (tercile 3) to less unequal ones (tercile 1). All data on income correspond, more precisely, to disposable income per consumption unit, i.e., net income after transfers divided by a coefficient depending on the size and members' age of households. We weight each municipality by its total population to give equal weight to each individual.

2.2. Empirical strategy

As a baseline, we estimate first the following empirical model:

8. A similar reasoning applies to net migration. However, the migration dataset from INSEE is only available for the census year. Thus, we cannot account for net migration in our analysis.

9. We only use French monitoring weather stations that conduct daily and regular observations by trained personnel.

$$M_{my} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 P_{my} + \mu X_{my} + \alpha_m + \varphi_y + \xi_{my}, \quad (2.1)$$

where M represents mortality rate for municipality m in year y . This mortality rate corresponds to the age-standardized mortality rate or is spread over 3 age categories. Coefficient β_1 measures the direct marginal effect of pollution exposure on M_{my} in a given municipality. P_{my} is a pollution variable that includes annual mean concentrations of PM_{10} as well as its corresponding thresholds. X_{my} is a vector of pollution controls as described in the previous section and in Panel C of Table 1. We also add temporal and spatial fixed effects. More particularly, we control for annual patterns by including a dummy variable for each year (φ_y). In the same vein, α_m controls for time-invariant specific municipal characteristics. ξ_{my} represents the error term.

As we are concerned with endogeneity issues, we also run an instrumental variable estimation. Drawing on recent literature in economics that uses quasi-experimental approaches to estimate the mortality effects of air pollution, we use wind direction as an instrumental variable for PM_{10} (Deryugina et al., 2019, Anderson, 2020). In line with Deryugina et al., 2019, our instruments are indicator variables for each 90-degree wind angle bin. We build dummies for each of the four following directions: North (below 45° or above 315°), East (between 45° and 135°), South (between 135° and 225°) and West (between 225° and 315°). Each variable in the set is equal to one if the yearly average wind direction in the municipality falls in the 90° degree interval and zero otherwise. The omitted category is the interval (225, 315). It is worth noticing that even if we average at the year level, the wind direction remains a strong predictor of air pollution levels. This is confirmed by the large first-stage F-statistics presented in our next tables.

3. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

3.1. *The impact of pollution on mortality rates*

We start by reporting the effect of pollution on the age-standardized mortality rate in Table 2. There is a straightforward relationship between PM_{10} and mortality rate. PM_{10} has a strong positive relationship with mortality outcomes: the higher the pollution concentration, the higher the mortality rate. Column 1 of Panel 1.1 shows that an increase of 1 microgram per cubic meter of PM_{10} is associated with a rise in the age-standardized mortality rate by 0.0364 per 100 000, without controlling for weather or economic characteristics beyond fixed effects. The coefficient stays roughly the same when controlling for additional weather characteristics (0.0393%000) and for both weather and median income (0.0386%000).

Given that the vulnerability to pollution is often found to vary by age, we present the results for three age-based subsamples in the following columns of Table 2. Columns 2, 3, and 4 display the

Table 2 – The impact of air pollution on mortality rates

	Age-standardized mortality rate	<15	15-49	=>50
Panel 1.1: without controls				
mean_PM ₁₀	0.036*** (0.006)	0.002 (0.001)	0.0003 (0.002)	0.051*** (0.017)
<i>N</i>	55716	52560	55716	55716
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.829	0.018	0.175	0.747
Panel 1.2: with weather controls				
mean_PM ₁₀	0.039*** (0.006)	0.002 (0.001)	0.0002 (0.002)	0.056*** (0.018)
Temperature	-0.0575* (0.034)	-0.008 (0.009)	0.015 (0.015)	-0.135 (0.097)
Precipitation	0.103*** (0.031)	0.002 (0.009)	-0.006 (0.012)	0.200** (0.086)
Maximum wind speed	-0.052 (0.032)	-0.002 (0.009)	-0.035*** (0.012)	-0.133 (0.088)
<i>N</i>	55716	52560	55716	55716
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.829	0.018	0.175	0.747
Panel 1.3: with weather, income and interquartile controls				
mean_PM ₁₀	.038*** (.006)	0.002 (.002)	0.0001 (0.002)	0.055*** (0.018)
Median income	-.00003 (.00001)	-0.000005 (0.000004)	-0.000004 (0.000005)	-0.0001** (0.00004)
Temperature	-.055 (.034)	-0.007 (0.009)	0.015 (0.015)	-0.130 (0.097)
Precipitation	.104*** (.031)	0.002 (0.009)	-0.006 (0.012)	0.204** (0.086)
Maximum wind speed	-.050 (.032)	-0.001 (0.009)	-0.034*** (0.012)	-0.129 (0.088)
<i>N</i>	55716	52560	55716	55716
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.829	0.018	0.175	0.747
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate and mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older.

estimation results for individuals under 15 years old, between 15 and 49 years old, and 50 years or older, respectively. We show that pollution significantly increases the mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older. More precisely, an increase of $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PM_{10} leads to a rise in mortality among individuals aged 50 and older by 0.055 per 100,000. As the impact on the other age-based subsamples is not significant, the overall effect of pollution on mortality is therefore driven by the elderly.

The same exercise is done using IV estimation. First, Table 3 presents the first-stage and reduced-form analysis of the IV approach, highlighting the negative effect of wind direction on pollution, and demonstrating that wind direction is a strong instrument (see the F test of excluded instruments). The second stage estimation, detailed in the last panel of Table 3, reveals that our previous results are robust but also strengthened under IV implementation. We observe a significant increase in the effect of pollution on the age-standardized mortality rate from 0.039 to 0.41%000. This result appears to be driven, once again, by the significant increase in the mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older, which rises from 0.05 to 0.85%000. In other words, an increase of $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PM_{10} leads to a rise in mortality rate among French people over 50 by 0.85 per 100,000.

Therefore, our findings provide strong evidence of a causal impact of PM_{10} on the age-standardized mortality rate, as well as on the mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older in France. To provide a monetary measure of the magnitude of this health impact, we rely on the value of the statistical life for individuals aged 50 or older in France, as estimated by Herrera-Araujo and Rochaix (2020).¹⁰ A back-of-the-envelope calculation suggests that the corresponding cost of exposure to PM_{10} in France amounts to 4.4 billion euros per year.¹¹

10. Note that their estimation of the value of statistical life of individuals aged 50 or older in France is equal to 4.85 million euros, which is smaller than the average value in the overall French population, i.e. 6.5 million euros.

11. This figure is obtained by combining the number of individuals of 50 or older in France in 2012 (4,519,556), the estimated marginal effect of pollution exposure (0.8529/100000), the value of statistical life of Herrera-Araujo and Rochaix (2020) (4.85 million euros), and the average concentration of PM_{10} ($23.57 \mu/\text{m}^3$). It corresponds to an annual cost of 187 million euros per μ/m^3 .

Table 3 – The impact of air pollution on mortality rates - IV approach

	Age-standardized mortality rate	<15	15-49	=>50
First stage: The impact of wind direction on PM ₁₀				
North wind mean direction	2.085 *** (.363)	2.018 *** (.204)	2.101*** (.203)	2.101 *** (.207)
East wind mean direction	.934 *** (.187)	1.058 *** (.223)	.921*** (.204)	.913 *** (.223)
South wind mean direction	.474*** (.033)	.450*** (.038)	.466*** (.037)	.493 *** (.037)
F-test of excluded instrument	31.03 ***	72.06***	80.48***	83.65***
Reduced form: The impact of wind direction on mortality rate				
North wind mean direction	.730 (.561)	0.040 (0.119)	0.205 (0.225)	1.644 (1.042)
East wind mean direction	.784** (.290)	0.078 (0.080)	-0.033 (0.121)	1.980** (0.897)
South wind mean direction	.189*** (.051)	0.004 (0.015)	-0.002 (0.018)	0.395*** (0.143)
Second stage: The impact of PM ₁₀ , instrumented by wind direction, on mortality rate				
mean_PM ₁₀	.416*** (.103)	0.016 (0.029)	0.005 (0.037)	0.868*** (0.25)
Median income	.00001 (.00002)	-0.000004 (0.000006)	-0.000004 (0.000007)	-0.00002 (0.00005)
Temperature	.104* (.056)	-0.001 (0.015)	0.017 (0.022)	0.222 (0.150)
Precipitation	.412*** (.09)	0.014 (0.025)	-0.002 (0.033)	0.869*** (0.223)
Maximum wind speed	-.047 (.033)	-0.001 (0.009)	-0.034*** (0.012)	-0.120 (0.09)
<i>N</i>	55716	52466	55607	55607
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.186	-0.070	-0.039	0.149
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the first stage, the reduced form, and the second stage of the IV estimation of the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate and mortality rate for different age categories. The different wind directions are used as instruments for PM₁₀. All estimates are relative to wind direction blowing from the west. The dummy corresponding to a wind direction at West (between 225 and 315), is considered as the reference category in this IV estimation. It is thus omitted.

3.2. The influence of inequality on environmental health

This Section examines whether inequality influences the causal effect of pollution on mortality. We begin by incorporating an inequality measure, i.e. the interquartile range, as a control variable in our IV estimation. Table 4 presents the results and indicates that inequality has a positive and significant effect on this relationship.¹²

Table 4 – The impact of air pollution on mortality rates - IV approach - with inequality as a control variable

	Age-standardized mortality rate	<15	15-49	=>50
Second stage: The impact of PM ₁₀ , instrumented by wind direction, on mortality rate				
mean_PM ₁₀	.409 *** (.103)	.015 (.029)	.004 (.0377)	.852*** (.251)
Median income	-.00004 * (.00002)	-.00001* (6.68e-06)	-.00001 * (8.39e-06)	-.0001*** (.00005)
Interquartile range	.0001 *** (.00001)	.00001 *** (4.50e-06)	.00001 *** (5.69e-06)	.0002 *** (.00004)
Temperature	.091 (.056)	-.003 (.015)	.015 (.022)	.193 (.149)
Precipitation	.409 *** (.090)	.013 (.025)	-.002 (.033)	.862*** (.222)
Maximum wind speed	-.044 (.033)	-.001 (.009)	-.034 *** (.012)	-.110 (.089)
<i>N</i>	55716	52466	55607	55607
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the second stage of the IV estimation of the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate and mortality rate for different age categories. The different wind directions are used as instruments for PM₁₀. All estimates are relative to wind direction blowing from the west. The dummy corresponding to a wind direction at West (between 225 and 315), is considered as the reference category in this IV estimation. It is thus omitted.

To further investigate this potential source of heterogeneity in the effect of PM₁₀ on mortality, we conduct an analysis based on terciles of inequality indicators per unit of consumption in line with Currie and Schwandt (2016) or Schwandt et al. (2022). The goal is to compare the health impact of PM₁₀ across municipalities with different levels of inequality. Table 5 presents the results for individuals aged 50 and older, identified in the previous subsection as the most vulnerable group. Each column corresponds to a subsample based on inequality terciles.

Specifically, the first tercile group includes municipalities in the bottom 33% of the distribution (i.e., the least unequal), the second tercile group represents municipalities with intermediary levels of inequality, and the third tercile group comprises municipalities in the top 33% of the distribution

12. Notably, the interquartile range exhibits the same positive and significant effect on the relationship between PM₁₀ and all mortality indicators in the standard estimation (without IV).

(i.e., the most unequal). Each of the four panels reports results for a specific inequality indicator.

Table 5 – The impact of air pollution on the mortality rate of individuals aged 50 and older by inequality indicators - IV approach

	50 years old or more		
	tercile1	tercile2	tercile3
INEQUALITY INDICATORS			
Panel Gini index			
mean_PM ₁₀	-0.122 (0.711)	1.397*** (0.508)	1.348*** (0.431)
<i>N</i>	18454	18213	18319
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.040	0.063	0.139
Panel interdecile d9/d1			
mean_PM ₁₀	-0.169 (0.637)	0.805* (0.437)	1.834*** (0.538)
<i>N</i>	20266	17455	17351
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.007	0.125	0.046
Panel interquartile range Q3-Q1			
mean_PM ₁₀	0.477 (0.525)	0.918** (0.403)	1.082* (0.601)
<i>N</i>	18431	18361	18227
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.091	0.086	0.067
Panel income share of the top 10 %			
mean_PM ₁₀	0.568 (0.739)	1.050** (0.464)	1.358*** (0.444)
<i>N</i>	18424	18212	18341
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.010	0.103	0.114
weather and income controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older by inequality indicators.

We show that the causal health effect of pollution varies with the level of inequality within municipalities. Specifically, pollution has no significant effect on the mortality rates in the 33% least unequal municipalities, whereas this effect is significant in the other municipalities and increases with the level of inequality. A 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in PM₁₀ in the third tercile of inequality leads to an increase in the mortality rate of approximately 1,35%000, 1,83%000, 1,08%000 and 1.36%000 for the Gini coefficient, interdecile ratio, interquartile range, and income share of the top 10%, respectively. These effects are up to twice as large as those for municipalities in the second tercile of the inequality distribution, with differences ranging from +17% to +125%, except for the Gini coefficient, which yields similar estimates for the second and third terciles.

As a robustness check, we replicate the analysis presented in Table 5 without controlling for median income. The results are presented in Table 8 of the Annex 7.2. They are identical in sign and significance, and very similar in terms of magnitude. The influence of inequality on pollution-related mortality is therefore not explained by a wealth effect. We also repeat the exercise using air pollution with a one-year lag. The Results are displayed in Table 9 of the Annex 7.2 and show that pollution has a lasting causal effect on individuals aged 50 and older, persisting for up to one year. This effect is particularly true and pronounced in the most unequal municipalities. Moreover, the differences across municipalities based on inequality levels are even larger than in the case of the immediate impact of pollution (same year).

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this section, we formalize a simple model to identify the potential mechanisms through which income inequality may amplify the detrimental effect of pollution on average health. The model represents a given municipality. Its main components are the presence of heterogeneous agents in terms of income, endogenous life expectancy determined by pollution exposure (which may vary within the municipality), and both private and public health expenditure. We will examine how these factors shape the economic behaviors of households and their aggregate effect on average health in the municipality.¹³

Each agent lives for two periods. In the first period, she works, saves, and invests in health, and is retired during the second period whose length depends on a longevity index. For simplicity, we assume that the size of each young generation is constant and equal to one. Therefore, we disregard the age distribution within the municipality, in line with our empirical analysis which uses the age-standardized mortality rate, and hence already controls for this confounder.

Individuals are indexed by $i = p, r$, corresponding to the two groups of individuals in the municipality: poor (p) and rich (r), of size ξ and $1 - \xi$, respectively. The two groups of agents differ in terms of income (a^i), which is exogenously determined by the family they come from ($a_t^p < a_t^r$). The average income in the area is thus given by:

$$\bar{a}_t = \xi a_t^p + (1 - \xi) a_t^r. \quad (4.1)$$

4.1. Consumer's utility and health

An individual of type i born in t cares about her consumption level when old c_{t+1}^i . We follow the assumption of Raffin and Seegmuller (2017) and abstract from consumption choices in the first

13. Since data on individual psychological behaviors at the municipal level in France are unavailable, we chose to disregard the impact of inequality through these factors.

period. The agent utility function is thus given by:

$$U(c_{t+1}^i, \pi_t^i) = \pi_t^i \ln(c_{t+1}^i). \quad (4.2)$$

The parameter $\pi_t^i \in [0, 1]$ represents the survival probability of the agent i when old, or equivalently, her longevity.¹⁴ A higher life expectancy π_t^i enhances individuals' welfare from consuming when old.

Longevity is an increasing function of the health index h_t^i . In accordance with empirical evidence, this health index depends positively on private health spending e_t^i and publicly funded health services S_t . Introducing public health allows us to consider the relationship between income inequality and the size of the public sector, a complex and debated topic. One proposed mechanism is that income inequality could affect not only the amount of available public funds but also voters' willingness to support taxation and public expenditures. However, empirical research has yet to reach a clear consensus on this relationship. While we do not aim to draw definitive conclusions on this matter, we offer a formalization that is sufficiently broad, where the policy scheme in place influences the relationship between inequality and the amount of public services.

In line with Bhattacharya and Qiao (2007) and Heer and Rohrbacher (2021), we assume complementary interaction between the public and private components of the health system. Moreover, as in Raffin and Seegmuller (2017), we assume that air pollution exposure reduces the efficiency of both types of health spending. However, in contrast to this paper, we incorporate pollution inequality by formalizing unequal vulnerability to pollution, through heterogeneous private health expenditures, and unequal exposure.

To align with the empirical analysis, we treat pollution in the area P_t as an exogenous variable. We intentionally set aside issues related to the determination of air pollution, as the empirical methodology is designed to address this endogeneity bias.¹⁵ However, we assume that exposure to air pollution within the municipality $\Theta^i P_t$ may be equal or unequal for poor and rich agents, with $\Theta^i \equiv \Theta(a^i) > 0$. In this latter case, the idea is that poor agents face greater financial constraints than rich agents, which limits their ability to choose their location. Nonetheless, an individual's income has a negative but concave impact on exposure, i.e., $\Theta'(a^i) < 0$ and $\Theta''(a^i) > 0$.

Private health spending includes healthcare and various expenditures aimed at improving health. Given the adverse effects of pollution, such spending mitigates vulnerability to a given level of

14. More precisely, an individual i born in t lives $1 + \pi_t^i$ period(s). Thus, we interchangeably use the terms "life expectancy", "longevity" and "survival probability" in this paper to characterize this variable.

15. A stronger exposure to particulate matter in unequal municipalities could explain a more harmful effect. To counteract such an endogeneity issue, we propose in the empirical analysis an instrumental estimation commonly used in this environmental health economic literature. Based on Deryugina et al. (2019) and Anderson (2020), we use wind as an instrument. As wind appears to be a strong instrument (see the F test of the excluded instrument) and Table 3 shows a significant effect of the impact of PM_{10} on mortality rate, for which we can rule out any endogeneity issues from this paper.

pollution exposure, and hence also encompasses pollution avoidance expenditures. Public health, on the other hand, refers to health infrastructure shared at the municipality level, such as the availability of medicines, hospital beds, and other healthcare resources.

For the sake of simplicity, we use the following functional form for the health index:

$$h_t^i = \frac{(e_t^i)^{1-\sigma} S_t^\sigma}{1 + \Theta^i P_t^\beta}, \quad (4.3)$$

with $\sigma \in (0, 1)$, and $\beta > 0$, capturing the toxicity of emissions. In the same way, we assume the following function for survival probability in old age, in line with Raffin and Seegmuller (2017):

$$\pi_t^i = \gamma \frac{h_t^i}{1 + h_t^i}, \quad (4.4)$$

such that life expectancy is increasing concave in health and achieves its maximum level $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ when the health index is infinitely high.

4.2. Optimal choices and average health

At adulthood, agents are endowed with a level of income a_t^i , depending on their type (rich, poor), which they allocate between private spending for healthcare (e_t^i) and savings for retirement (s_t^i). In the retirement period, agents only consume their income from savings. Thus, the budget constraints of an adult i during adulthood and old age are respectively given by:

$$e_t^i + s_t^i = (1 - \tau^i) a_t^i, \quad (4.5)$$

$$c_{t+1}^i = s_t^i R, \quad (4.6)$$

with $\tau^i > 0$, the individual income tax rate, and $R > 0$, the return on savings.

An adult maximizes her utility while considering her budget constraint in both periods (4.5) and (4.6), as well as the impact of her decisions on her health, as defined by (4.3) and (4.4). Her optimal choices satisfy:

$$\frac{e_t^i(1 + h_t^i)}{(1 - \tau^i)a_t^i - e_t^i} = (1 - \sigma) [\ln(R) + \ln((1 - \tau^i)a_t^i - e_t^i)].$$

Private health spending enhances longevity, thereby increasing incentives to save. However, it also competes directly with savings in the budget constraint. Since the latter effect dominates, a unique equilibrium e_t^i exists. Thus, the agent's investment in health corresponds to:

$$e_t^i \equiv e(a_t^i, S_t, P_t). \quad (4.7)$$

It increases with pollution P_t and decreases with public health services S_t . The lower the public health services and the higher the pollution, the greater the private health spending, due to their respective negative and positive effects on the health index h_t^i . Individual income (a_t^i) has a direct positive effect on private health spending by expanding the agent's budget. However, it also has an indirect negative effect by reducing exposure to pollution, thereby reducing the need for private health expenditure. Since the marginal impact of income on health diminishes, private health spending always increases with a_t^i .

Public authority implements taxes on income to fund public health spending S_t . It balances its budget such that:

$$S_t = \tau^p a_t^p \xi + \tau^r a_t^r (1 - \xi).$$

We consider a tax system that can either be progressive, regressive, or proportional to income. We thus assume $0 < \tau^p, \tau^r < 1$ and $\tau^p \leq$ or $\geq \tau^r$.

Defining the inequality index as $x = a^r/a^p$, individual income can be written as:

$$a_t^p = \frac{\bar{a}_t}{\xi + x_t(1 - \xi)} \quad \text{and} \quad a_t^r = \frac{\bar{a}_t}{\xi/x_t + (1 - \xi)}. \quad (4.8)$$

Thus, public health corresponds to a function of income distribution and average income, reflecting how both the overall economic environment and the distribution of income within a municipality may influence the availability and effectiveness of public health services:

$$S_t = \bar{a}_t \left(\frac{\tau^p \xi}{\xi + x_t(1 - \xi)} + \frac{\tau^r (1 - \xi)}{\xi/x_t + (1 - \xi)} \right) \equiv f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t). \quad (4.9)$$

It is increasing in \bar{a}_t , and varies with x depending on the tax system: it increases (or decreases) with x if $\tau^r > \tau^p$ (or $\tau^r < \tau^p$), or is independent of x if $\tau^r = \tau^p$. For a given average income, an increase in inequality raises public funds if the tax system is progressive. However, considering that an increase in inequality is typically associated with a shift in average income, the outcome becomes ambiguous, as we observe the following:

$$\text{sign} \frac{\partial S_t}{\partial x_t} = (\xi + x_t(1 - \xi)) \frac{\partial \bar{a}_t}{\partial x_t} [\xi \tau^p + (1 - \xi) x_t \tau^r] + \bar{a}_t \xi (1 - \xi) (\tau^r - \tau^p). \quad (4.10)$$

$\frac{\partial \bar{a}_t}{\partial x_t}$ may be either positive or negative, depending on the source of the inequality. Thus, even when $\tau^r - \tau^p > 0$ (progressive tax system), this is not clear if more unequal area are characterized by better public health services. We will discuss the different configurations and their implications for our analysis in the following section.

Finally, we are interested in the average health index defined as:

$$\bar{\pi}_t = \xi \pi_t^p + (1 - \xi) \pi_t^r,$$

which can be rewritten as:

$$\bar{\pi}_t = \xi \gamma \frac{h_t^p}{1 + h_t^p} + (1 - \xi) \gamma \frac{h_t^r}{1 + h_t^r}. \quad (4.11)$$

The individual health indices h^r and h^p depend on public spending, private individual spending, and pollution exposure, as described by (4.3). To continue the analysis, we define all individual outcomes as functions of inequality x and average income \bar{a} , using (4.8). Individual exposure can thus be written as:

$$\Theta(a_t^i) \equiv \Gamma^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t), \quad (4.12)$$

and using (4.7) and (4.9), the agent's investment in health is:

$$e_t^i \equiv \mathcal{E}^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t). \quad (4.13)$$

By substituting individual choices from (4.13) and public health spending from (4.9) into (4.3), and utilizing (4.11), we derive the following function for average health:

$$\bar{\pi}_t = \gamma (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma \times \left(\frac{\xi (\mathcal{E}^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma}}{1 + \Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta + (\mathcal{E}^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma} (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma} + \frac{(1 - \xi) (\mathcal{E}^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma}}{1 + \Gamma^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta + (\mathcal{E}^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma} (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma} \right).$$

It is worth noticing that average health cannot be expressed as a function solely dependent on average income \bar{a}_t .

Even if we assume that inequality has no direct effect on the variables, our simple model identifies several channels through which distribution matters for the average health in the area, beyond the overall or average income level.

First, the size of each group (captured by ξ): If group sizes differ, the individual-level link between income and health alone is sufficient to observe an aggregate link between average health and inequality.

Second, the curvilinear association between income and health at the individual level (captured by $\mathcal{E}^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t)^{1-\sigma}$): Given our formalization of the utility function and health index, the marginal benefit of income on health outcomes is higher for lower-income individuals, reflecting a concavity effect.

Third, the way taxes are collected determines the availability and funding of public health services ($f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t)$). As highlighted earlier, if taxes are income-dependent, the total amount of public funds

is not a simple function of average income, but may be positively or negatively affected by inequality, depending on the tax system.

Fourth, unequal exposure to pollution (captured by $\Gamma^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t)$): If pollution exposure differs among poor and rich individuals, such disparity may explain the impact of inequality on average health.

4.3. The effect of pollution on average health

Our simple model with private and public health expenditure, pollution exposure, heterogeneous agents in terms of income is able to describe aggregate channels through which inequality may shape average health. In this subsection, we examine the specific mechanisms related to environmental health, i.e. whether and how inequality can shape the impact of pollution on average health. To address this question, we first emphasize the effect of pollution on aggregate health in our equilibrium model by computing the elasticity of average health to pollution $\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P}$, which is the weighted sum of the individual elasticities:

$$\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P} = \xi \frac{\partial \pi^p}{\partial P} \frac{P}{\pi^p} + (1 - \xi) \frac{\partial \pi^r}{\partial P} \frac{P}{\pi^r}.$$

Thus, we obtain:

LEMMA 1. *The magnitude of the elasticity of average survival probability to pollution is given by:*

$$|\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P}| = \left(\xi \frac{\overbrace{\beta \Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta}^{\text{direct negative effect}} - \overbrace{(1 - \sigma) \epsilon^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t) (1 + \Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta)}^{\text{compensation effect}}}{1 + \Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta + (\mathcal{E}^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma} (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma} \right. \quad (4.14)$$

$$\left. + (1 - \xi) \frac{\overbrace{\beta \Gamma^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta}^{\text{direct negative effect}} - \overbrace{(1 - \sigma) \epsilon^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t) (1 + \Gamma^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta)}^{\text{compensation effect}}}{1 + \Gamma^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta + (\mathcal{E}^r(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma} (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma} \right), \quad (4.15)$$

with $\epsilon^i = \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^i}{\partial P} \frac{P}{\mathcal{E}^i} > 0$, the elasticity of private spending to pollution.

Proof. See Appendix 7.1. □

We highlight two theoretical opposite effects of pollution on the average longevity of individuals in a given municipality: one direct and negative, and one indirect and positive. The magnitude of the direct effect depends on exposure to pollution, which may vary between populations. The indirect effect arises from the behavior of agents who mitigate the negative impact of pollution. This marginal positive effect of pollution on health, occurring through adjustments of private spending, reduces the direct negative effect. However, the term $|(1 - \sigma)\epsilon^i|$ implies that private spending is

insufficient to fully offset the direct negative effect, which is consistent with our empirical results showing that pollution has a positive effect on mortality.

Related to our empirical analysis, our objective is to examine whether the vulnerability to pollution differs across municipalities with varying levels of inequality. From an analytical point of view, this corresponds to examining how an increase in x affects $\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P}$. In Section 4.2, we already explained why inequality matters for determining average health. Here, we go one step further by examining how inequality specifically shapes the average health effect of pollution. To achieve this, we need to consider the different configurations that can characterize a municipality with higher inequality and their implications for average income. Figure 1 summarizes the different sources of higher inequality and the channels through which x affects $|\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P}|$. Our findings reinforce the mechanisms mentioned earlier, showing that average health depends not only on average income but also on income distribution, and thus on inequality. Even if all key variables depend solely on income and/or pollution, without incorporating behavioral factors —such as psychological mechanisms or political responses (e.g., voting)-, this simple model highlights mechanisms through which distribution matters for the average environmental health in the area, beyond its effect on average income. The key reasons identified in our model are as follows:

Channels		Configurations characterizing a more unequal municipality		
		Case 1: $\uparrow a_r > \uparrow a_p \geq 0$	Case 2: $\downarrow a_p > \downarrow a_r \geq 0$	Case 3: $\uparrow a_r$ and $\downarrow a_p$
Average income \bar{a}		–	+	+ if $\xi > 1 - \xi$ – if $\xi < 1 - \xi$
Exposure to pollution Γ^i		–	+	Poor: + Rich: –
Private health spending ϵ^i		–	+	Poor: + Rich: –
Elasticity of private spending to pollution ϵ^i		?	?	?
Public health spending f^S	Proportional tax system	–	+	+ if $\xi > 1 - \xi$ – if $\xi < 1 - \xi$
	Progressive tax system			? if $\xi > 1 - \xi$ – if $\xi < 1 - \xi$
	Regressive tax system			+ if $\xi > 1 - \xi$? if $\xi < 1 - \xi$

Figure 1 – Effect of an increase in x on the vulnerability of average health to pollution $|\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P}|$ through the channels indicated in lines, depending on the source of inequality in columns.

Note: A situation marked with "?" indicates an uncertain impact, depending on the model's specifications.

First, pollution exposure varies between rich and poor agents, due to differing abilities to locate in cleaner neighborhoods. Individual exposure is assumed to depend on income, so any change in

inequality that alters the relative income between the rich and poor will mechanically modify the effect of pollution on average health. The importance of this effect depends on the existence of unequal exposure to air pollution within municipalities.

Second, given the positive relationship between health spending and income, a change in x may affect the amount of private health spending, while these expenditures diminish the effect of pollution on longevity. Accordingly, x can either amplify or reduce the effect of pollution on average health, depending on the source of inequality and the size of each income group within the municipality.

Third, x also affects the elasticity of private spending to pollution, which determines the magnitude of the compensation effect. The impact of x on this channel remains ambiguous in our model.

Fourth, income distribution among the population may influence public support for health services, depending on the tax system. Greater inequality under a progressive taxation regime could indeed generate more revenue for the municipality, which could be invested in healthcare infrastructure.

All these channels are related to the impact of inequality on individual and average income (see Section 4.2). However, the net effect of inequality depends on the sign and magnitude of these different channels, as well as on the source of increased inequality. Indeed, higher inequality can correspond to the poorest segment of the population becoming poorer [Cases 2 and 3 in Figure 1], or to both poor and rich populations becoming wealthier while the income gap between them also widens [Case 1 in Figure 1]. The sign of each channel can vary significantly depending on the situation. When municipalities with greater inequality are characterized by wealthier populations being richer while the poor are not poorer, our simple model predicts that these municipalities should exhibit lower population vulnerability to pollution [Case 1]. Conversely, if everyone is poorer in the more unequal area, the average vulnerability of the population should be larger, *ceteris paribus* [Case 2]. Finally, in a municipality where the rich are richer while the poor are poorer, it remains unclear whether the average vulnerability to pollution is greater or lower compared to a more equal one [Case 3]. In this scenario, both groups experience changes in opposite directions regarding their exposure and financial capacity for healthcare expenditures. The average effect will thus depend on the relative sizes of these groups, but not only on that. Even if the absolute variation is the same for both and their sizes are equivalent, diminishing marginal returns to health imply that the consequences of a given income variation will differ. Finally, this average effect also depends on the taxation system, with inequalities being more harmful under a regressive system. Thus, Case 3 shows that even if higher inequality is associated with higher average income, it does not necessarily lead to a reduction of average vulnerability to pollution.

5. TESTING THE DIFFERENT CHANNELS

Our analysis reveals that counties with greater inequality suffer from a stronger impact of particulate matter PM_{10} on mortality rates. This section is coming back to the empirical analysis to test the different channels proposed by the model. Before confronting the mechanisms highlighted by the model with the data, it is useful to understand the intuitive mechanisms that are not considered in the model because they have already been neutralized in the empirical analysis. Typically, the existing literature highlights the greater vulnerability of the elderly to pollution. Variations in the age distribution across inequality terciles could then drive differences in vulnerability between municipalities. Yet, we address this potential confounder using age-standardized mortality rates in all estimates, effectively neutralizing any effects arising from disparities in age distribution. Moreover, additional differences in time-invariant municipal characteristics - such as being rural or urban, or varied occupational profile of the population - as well as temporal factors, including inflation (which affects households' purchasing power) or epidemics, may also serve as potential explanatory variables. However, these factors are fully accounted for through our individual and temporal fixed effects, ensuring a comprehensive control of potential confounders. Finally, note that the straightforward effect going through average income has already been neutralized in the empirical analysis. Indeed, unequal municipalities could be poorer than their more equitable counterparts. However, our analyses address this concern by controlling for median income at the municipal level, ensuring the robustness of our findings.¹⁶

The other mechanisms can therefore be grouped under three headings: public health spending, pollution exposure, and private health spending. We explore each of these in the following subsections.

5.1. *Public health expenditures*

The model shows that inequality can influence the health effects of pollution through its impact on public health expenditures. If the latter is negative, it could explain - at least partly - why unequal municipalities suffer more from pollution-related mortality.

The French healthcare system is predominantly publicly funded and managed at the national level, with health coverage for the entire population and nationally set reimbursement rates for medical services and treatments (Social Security system), public hospitals, public health programs, etc.¹⁷ However, local authorities may also play a crucial role in the healthcare supply, by financing infrastructure and services or providing incentives to attract healthcare professionals such as instal-

16. We will control for additional poverty indices in Section 5.3.

17. While the Social Security system covers a significant part of healthcare costs, out-of-pocket expenses can still be a burden for a part of the population - especially depending on whether doctors adhere (or not) to the established tariffs set by Social Security.

lation aids or free zones (i.e. tax benefits for those who settle in these areas). Therefore, we will employ two proxy variables, from the INSEE facility database, to gauge the extent of municipal support for health, i.e., health equipment and the average number of doctors per 100.000 inhabitants, and assess whether it could explain the observed effect of inequality. More precisely, we calculate an indicator of access to healthcare facilities by dividing the total number of health equipment in a municipality by its population, and an indicator of access to doctors by dividing the number of doctors in a municipality by its population. In order to take into account access to neighboring structures, we repeat table 5 exercise with clustering at the municipal error level. This accounts for possible correlations between municipalities. Table 10 in Annex 7.2 shows that the significance remains rather stable.¹⁸

Figures 2 and 3 show no relationship between the interquartile range and the latter indicators. Indeed, a low level of inequality is associated with all types of healthcare expenditures and access to physicians. Therefore, we cannot establish a conclusive relationship between inequality and access to healthcare.

Figure 2 – Relationship between inequality and access to healthcare.

Figure 3 – Relationship between inequality and access to doctors.

5.2. Unequal exposure to air pollution

The variation of pollution can be considered endogenous between and within municipalities. First, unequal municipalities could exhibit a larger exposure to particulate matter, explaining a larger pollution burden. Nevertheless, our instrumental variable strategy allows us to remove the idea that pollution is higher in unequal municipalities. Moreover, we find no differences in pollution exposure between municipalities according to their level of inequality (see Figure 4).

¹⁸. except for tercile 2 in the interquartile range

Figure 4 – Evolution of PM_{10} between municipalities according to their level of inequality.

Second, as the model suggests, unequal exposure to pollution among agents within municipalities may also represent a channel through which inequality exacerbates the detrimental effect of pollution on life expectancy. Empirical studies usually find that lower-income households suffer from a larger exposure to air pollution (see e.g. Jbaily et al., 2022). But while it is clear for the US, the results are mixed when dealing with Europe (see, e.g., Hajat et al., 2015; Gosztonyi et al., 2023). For France, Bez et al. (2024) have recently examined the relationship between income at the municipality level and the location of industrial brownfields, and concluded at an inverted U shape. Here, we contribute to the literature by examining unequal exposure to PM pollution within French municipalities. We compute the interquartile ratio of average exposure to PM_{10} within municipalities from 2007 to 2015, due to data availability. Figure 5 shows the distribution of the interquartile ratio of average exposure to PM_{10} within municipalities, i.e. the ratio of the exposure of the 25% richest to the exposure of the 25% poorest within municipalities. The distribution in peak reveals a quasi-absence of unequal exposure to PM pollution within French municipalities. More precisely, the exposure to particulate matter of the bottom 25% is similar to the exposure of the top 25% within a given municipality.

5.3. Private health expenditure and poverty effect

Another potential mechanism relies on private health expenditure. The model emphasizes that inequality affects the elasticity of health to pollution, through health spending. Given a specific healthcare system and institutional context, private health expenditures inherently depend on two key dimensions: individuals' financial means and their choices/preferences.

We first examine the financial aspect by exploring the potential role of poverty within a municipality, both in terms of its prevalence within the population and its intensity. More unequal municipalities may have a higher proportion of poor individuals, or poorer households compared to other areas, even when median income remains the same. Since poorer agents are empirically found

Figure 5 – The distribution of inequalities in terms of average exposure to PM_{10} within municipalities.

Note: This figure shows the distribution of the ratio of the exposure to PM_{10} of the 25% richest to the exposure of the 25% poorest within municipalities.

to be more vulnerable (Arceo et al., 2016), such a poverty effect could explain a low average environmental health. To examine the potential role of the prevalence of poverty within a municipality, we use the share of taxed households as a proxy for the opposite of the share of poor households in a given municipality. INSEE provides this data, representing the percentage of taxable households that pay income tax (IRPP). The results are presented in Table 6. The sign, significance, and magnitude of our findings remain robust when this proxy is included as a control variable.¹⁹

To account for the intensity of poverty, we redo our estimation while controlling for the level of the first decile of the income distribution in each municipality, corresponding to the maximum income of the bottom 10%. The results, presented in Table 7, remain robust to introducing this proxy as a control variable, as all the signs, significance, and magnitude of the PM_{10} coefficients are unchanged. We conclude that our result that inequality influences pollution-related mortality is not driven by a poverty effect.

Since inequalities are not associated with a deepening of poverty among the poorest segment of the population, we find ourselves in Case 1 discussed in the previous section. As a result, the model predicts that inequality should reduce pollution-related mortality, whereas we empirically observe the opposite. Therefore, the comparison between our theoretical model and empirical results suggests that the effect of inequality on vulnerability to pollution may be due to individuals' choices in terms of private health expenditure (including medical care and avoidance behavior), and hence the determinants and/or effectiveness of such spending (in addition to income and pollution). Although our analysis is conducted at a low level of aggregation (municipality) on an entire country, it does

¹⁹. The coefficient remains equivalent for all inequality indices, except the interquartile range (where tercile 3 is no longer significant).

Table 6 – The impact of air pollution on the mortality rate of individuals aged 50 and older by inequality indicators - IV approach and controlling for the share of taxed households (PMIMP)

	50 years old or more		
	tercile1	tercile2	tercile3
INEQUALITIES INDICATORS			
Panel Gini index			
mean_PM10	0.0822 (0.754)	1.054** (0.497)	1.336*** (0.441)
PMIMP	-0.0926*** (0.0358)	-0.140*** (0.0406)	-0.0466 (0.0386)
<i>N</i>	17865	16756	16806
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.039	0.112	0.168
Panel interdecile d9/d1			
mean_PM10	-0.186 (0.655)	0.657 (0.417)	1.935*** (0.580)
PMIMP	-0.0182 (0.0352)	-0.192*** (0.0391)	-0.0237 (0.0425)
<i>N</i>	19678	16060	15774
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.007	0.149	0.058
Panel interquartile range Q3-Q1			
mean_PM10	0.435 (0.630)	0.832** (0.409)	0.902 (0.552)
PMIMP	-0.0577 (0.0408)	-0.111*** (0.0359)	0.0271 (0.0605)
<i>N</i>	16452	17327	17524
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.102	0.102	0.100
Panel Income share of the top 10 %			
mean_PM10	0.345 (0.858)	0.790* (0.457)	1.318*** (0.444)
PMIMP	-0.0566 (0.0365)	-0.162*** (0.0373)	-0.0354 (0.0377)
<i>N</i>	17817	16874	16710
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.004	0.133	0.152
weather controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older by income and inequality indicators, controlling for the share of taxed households (PMIMP).

Table 7 – The impact of air pollution on the mortality rate of individuals aged 50 and older by inequality indicators - IV approach and controlling for the first income decile (rfucd1)

	50 years old or more		
	tercile1	tercile2	tercile3
INEQUALITIES INDICATORS			
Panel Gini index			
mean_PM ₁₀	-0.149 (0.707)	1.400*** (0.512)	1.356*** (0.430)
rfucd1	-0.000497*** (0.000147)	-0.000188 (0.000151)	0.000251 (0.000173)
<i>N</i>	18454	18213	18319
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.039	0.063	0.137
Panel interdecile d9/d1			
mean_PM ₁₀	-0.178 (0.637)	0.820* (0.435)	1.841*** (0.536)
rfucd1	-0.000357** (0.000151)	-0.000347** (0.000149)	0.000580*** (0.000224)
<i>N</i>	20266	17455	17351
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.007	0.124	0.046
Panel interquartile range Q3-Q1			
mean_PM ₁₀	0.493 (0.527)	0.932** (0.403)	1.094* (0.595)
rfucd1	-0.000766*** (0.000133)	0.000178 (0.000174)	0.0000762 (0.000123)
<i>N</i>	18431	18361	18227
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.090	0.084	0.065
Panel income share of the top 10 %			
mean_PM ₁₀	0.518 (0.733)	1.055** (0.464)	1.375*** (0.445)
rfucd1	-0.000431*** (0.000135)	-0.000185 (0.000129)	0.000283* (0.000156)
<i>N</i>	18424	18212	18341
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.007	0.102	0.111
weather controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older by income and inequality indicators, controlling for the first decile of income.

not enable us to test hypotheses based on individual characteristics. A complementary analysis is therefore needed to explore further this channel.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we conduct an empirical analysis of more than 35,000 French municipalities between 2000 and 2015 to test whether inequality may affect individuals' vulnerability to pollution. While the existing literature largely focuses on the impact of income on this relationship, we examine the potential role of income distribution within the population.

First, we show that particulate matter PM_{10} has a significant positive effect on mortality rates in France, in particular for individuals aged 50 or older. Using wind direction as an instrumental variable for pollution, we confirm the causal effect of pollution on mortality in this context. We then explore how this relationship is influenced by the level of inequality. This is the first study to analyze the effect of income inequality on health vulnerability to pollution at a low level of aggregation (i.e., municipality level). We find that the health effects of pollution increase with the level of income inequality within municipalities. More precisely, the effect of PM_{10} on mortality of individuals aged 50 or older in the top 33% most unequal municipalities is up to twice as large as the impact observed in municipalities with intermediary levels of inequality, while not significant in the 33% least unequal municipalities. To provide insight into the magnitude of this effect, we estimate the corresponding cost based on the value of statistical life. Our back-of-the-envelope calculation indicates that the cost of exposure to PM_{10} on mortality in France amounts to 4.4 billion euros per year, with two-thirds of this cost being incurred by municipalities in the top 33% most unequal. Therefore, inequality appears to play a significant role in environmental health, even in a country like France that exhibits relatively low levels of inequality.

Second, we develop a simple model to identify the potential underlying mechanisms responsible for such an effect at the municipality level. Our theoretical results highlight three main channels, in addition to other factors captured by the model's parameters. First, inequality may affect the public support for health in municipalities. Second, it may result from unequal exposure to pollution, due to varying abilities to relocate associated with agents' income. Third, it may stem from differences in private health expenditure, as both its amount and elasticity to pollution evolve with income.

Finally, we empirically test these potential mechanisms. We show that the impact of inequality on environmental health is not explained by differences in public health expenditure between municipalities, nor by higher exposure to particulate matter in unequal counties, or unequal exposure within them. Regarding private health expenditure, we decompose it into two components - financial means and choices. Inequality may affect the financial resources of households, exacerbating the incidence and severity of poverty, thereby limiting the ability to invest in healthcare. However, we

find that such a mechanism does not explain the observed patterns, as our results remain robust to controlling for both the prevalence and intensity of poverty. Therefore, we conclude that individuals' choices regarding private expenditures enhancing health (including, e.g., preventive and curative medical care, diet, sport, avoidance behaviors) and their determinants and/or effectiveness may represent a key explanatory factor. While our analysis is performed at a low level of aggregation on an entire country, it does not allow us to test hypotheses based on individual characteristics. Despite diverse results, the existing literature on health and inequality emphasizes several potentially relevant mechanisms that warrant further investigation in the context of environmental health. Typically, private health spending may be influenced by inequality, as individuals may accumulate debt, work longer hours, or reallocate resources away from health-related activities to engage in conspicuous consumption, as described by the “keeping up with the Joneses” effect (Alpizar et al., 2005; Allen and Chakraborty, 2018 or Japaridze and Sayour, 2021). Other mechanisms linked to psychological or institutional factors could also be considered. For example, relative deprivation may deteriorate health by inducing stress, frustration, and risky behavior (Wilkinson, 1996, Eibner and Evans, 2005, Mangyo and Park, 2011). Inequality may also influence how we are treated or cared for, as empirical studies provide evidence of discrimination in the healthcare system (see e.g., Johnston and Lordan, 2012 or Turner et al., 2022). Even if reconciling a large sample (entire country) with individual data is not simple, these are promising avenues for further research that could provide valuable insights into how inequality influences individuals' vulnerability to pollution.

7. APPENDIX

7.1. Theoretical insights: Proof of Lemma 1

The elasticity of average health to pollution $\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P}$ is given by:

$$\epsilon_{\bar{\pi}/P} = \xi \frac{\partial \pi^p}{\partial P} \frac{P}{\pi^p} + (1 - \xi) \frac{\partial \pi^r}{\partial P} \frac{P}{\pi^r}.$$

Based on (4.3), (4.4), (4.9), (4.12) and (4.13), we obtain individual mortality as a function of average health, inequality and pollution:

$$\pi_t^i = \gamma (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma \times \frac{(\mathcal{E}^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma}}{1 + \Gamma^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta + (\mathcal{E}^i(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma} (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma}.$$

Defining the elasticity of private spending to pollution as $\epsilon^i = \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^i}{\partial P} \frac{P}{\mathcal{E}^i}$, we have:

$$\frac{\partial \pi_t^i}{\partial P_t} = P^{-1} \left(\pi_t^i \frac{(1 - \sigma) \epsilon^i (1 + (\Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t)^\beta) - \beta \Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta}{1 + \Gamma^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t) P_t^\beta + (\mathcal{E}^p(x_t, \bar{a}_t, P_t))^{1-\sigma} (f^S(x_t, \bar{a}_t))^\sigma} \right).$$

We thus directly obtain the expression presented in Lemma 1.

7.2. Empirical Robustness checks

Table 8 – The impact of air pollution on the mortality rate of individuals aged 50 and older by inequality indicators - IV approach and without controlling for the median income

	50 years old or more		
	tercile1	tercile2	tercile3
INEQUALITIES INDICATORS			
Panel Gini index			
mean_PM10	-0.125 (0.711)	1.385*** (0.514)	1.366*** (0.436)
<i>N</i>	18454	18213	18319
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.040	0.065	0.135
Panel interdecile d9/d1			
mean_PM10	-0.179 (0.637)	0.797* (0.438)	1.875*** (0.552)
<i>N</i>	20266	17455	17351
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.007	0.126	0.036
Panel interquartile range Q3-Q1			
mean_PM10	0.504 (0.529)	0.921** (0.396)	1.112* (0.607)
<i>N</i>	18431	18361	18227
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.088	0.085	0.062
Panel income share of the top 10 %			
mean_PM10	0.537 (0.736)	1.039** (0.463)	1.385*** (0.452)
<i>N</i>	18424	18212	18341
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.009	0.104	0.109
weather controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older by income and inequality indicators, without controlling for the median income.

Table 9 – The impact of lag 1 air pollution on the mortality rate of individuals aged 50 and older by inequality indicators, with IV approach and controlling for the median income

	50 years old or more		
	tercile1	tercile2	tercile3
INEQUALITIES INDICATORS			
Panel Gini index			
L.mean_PM ₁₀	-0.336	0.753	1.151***
	(1.091)	(0.585)	(0.384)
<i>N</i>	17627	16615	16733
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.046	0.130	0.179
Panel interdecile d9/d1			
L.mean_PM ₁₀	-0.358	0.913**	1.705***
	(1.337)	(0.391)	(0.545)
<i>N</i>	19314	15953	15771
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.011	0.119	0.092
Panel interquartile range Q3-Q1			
L.mean_PM ₁₀	0.462	0.901*	1.555***
	(0.559)	(0.506)	(0.561)
<i>N</i>	16170	17173	17447
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.099	0.085	-0.024
Panel income share of the top 10 %			
L.mean_PM ₁₀	0.621	0.142	1.479***
	(1.207)	(0.437)	(0.460)
<i>N</i>	17564	16739	16630
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.016	0.158	0.109
weather and income controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older by income and inequality indicators, controlling for the median income.

Table 10 – The impact of air pollution on the mortality rate of individuals aged 50 and older by inequality indicators, with IV approach, and standard errors clustered at the municipal level.

	50 years old or more		
	tercile1	tercile2	tercile3
INEQUALITIES INDICATORS			
Panel Gini index			
mean_PM ₁₀	-0.122 (0.751)	1.397** (0.552)	1.348*** (0.448)
<i>N</i>	18454	18213	18319
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.040	0.063	0.139
Panel interdecile d9/d1			
mean_PM ₁₀	-0.169 (0.686)	0.805* (0.430)	1.834*** (0.574)
<i>N</i>	20266	17455	17351
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.007	0.125	0.046
Panel interquartile range Q3-Q1			
mean_PM ₁₀	0.477 (0.558)	0.918** (0.411)	1.082 (0.697)
<i>N</i>	18431	18361	18227
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.091	0.086	0.067
Panel income share of the top 10 %			
mean_PM ₁₀	0.568 (0.867)	1.050** (0.475)	1.358*** (0.469)
<i>N</i>	18424	18212	18341
adj. <i>R</i> ²	-0.010	0.103	0.114
weather and income controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: This table shows the impact of PM₁₀ on the age-standardized mortality rate for individuals aged 50 or older by income and inequality indicators, controlling for the median income. Clustering is done at the municipal level.

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